

SECOND ORDER PURE LAGRANGE-GALERKIN METHODS FOR FLUID-STRUCTURE INTERACTION PROBLEMS

MARTA BENÍTEZ[†] AND ALFREDO BERMÚDEZ[‡]

Abstract. In this paper we propose a pure Lagrange-Galerkin method for the numerical solution of fluid-structure interaction problems. The proposed scheme is written in material coordinates and in terms of displacements in the structure and of displacements and pressure in the fluid. Pure-Lagrangian displacement methods are useful for solving free surface problems and fluid-structure interaction problems because the computational domain is independent of time and fluid-structure coupling at the interphase is straightforward. Unfortunately, for moderate to high-Reynolds number flows, pure-Lagrangian methods can lead to high distortion of the mesh elements and as a consequence non-accurate approximations can be obtained. Before this happens it is necessary to re-mesh and re-initialize the motion. In the present paper we also deal with this problem by proposing a method to be combined with the pure Lagrange-Galerkin method we introduce that preserves the order. In order to assess the performance of the overall numerical method, we solve different problems in two space dimensions. In particular, numerical results for the motion of an elastic circular disk in a fluid and a sloshing problem with an elastic submerged ball in a rectangular tank are presented.

Key words. fluid-structure interaction problems, Navier-Stokes equations, linear elasticity, Lagrange-Galerkin methods, second-order schemes, pure-Lagrangian methods, semi-Lagrangian methods

AMS subject classifications.

1. Introduction. The main goal of the present paper is to introduce new second-order pure-Lagrangian methods for the numerical solution of fluid-structure interaction problems. For scalar convection-diffusion problems with dominant convection, methods of characteristics for time discretization problems are extensively used (see the review paper [14]). These methods are based on time discretization of the material time derivative and were introduced in the beginning of the eighties of the last century combined with finite differences or finite elements for space discretization (see [13], [18], [7]). In this context they are also called Lagrange-Galerkin methods. The classical methods of characteristics are written in Eulerian coordinates and they are also called semi-Lagrangian schemes. These methods have been mathematically analyzed and applied to different problems by several authors (see [13], [18], [21], [19], [8], [9] and [3]). More precisely, in [21] and [18] the classical first order characteristic method, as introduced in [13], is combined with finite elements for solving convection-diffusion equations. Moreover, estimates of the form $O(h^k) + O(\Delta t)$ in the $l^\infty(L^2(\mathbb{R}^d))$ -norm are shown in [21], where Δt denotes the time step, h the mesh-size, k the degree of the finite element space and d the dimension of the spatial domain. In [18] error estimates of the form $O(h^k) + O(\Delta t) + O(h^{k+1}/\Delta t)$ in the $l^\infty(L^2(\Omega))$ -norm are obtained under the assumption that the normal velocity vanishes on the boundary of Ω . All of these estimates involve constants depending on solution norms. In [19] a second order characteristics method for solving constant coefficient convection-diffusion equations with Dirichlet boundary conditions is studied. The Crank-Nicholson discretization has been used to approximate the material time derivative. For a divergence-free velocity field vanishing on the boundary and a smooth enough solution, stability and $O(\Delta t^2) + O(h^k)$ error estimates in the $l^\infty(L^2(\Omega))$ -norm are stated (see also [8] and [9] for further analysis).

Recently, we have introduced so-called *pure-Lagrangian methods* combined with finite elements, first for scalar linear convection-diffusion equations and then for vector nonlinear convection-diffusion equations. In particular, for scalar linear convection-diffusion equations, a second order pure Lagrange-Galerkin scheme has been introduced in [4] and [5] where $l^\infty(H^1(\Omega))$ stability and $l^\infty(H^1(\Omega))$ error estimates of order $O(\Delta t^2) + O(h^k)$ were proved. Moreover, in [12], semi-Lagrangian and pure-Lagrangian methods are proposed and analyzed for convection-diffusion equations. Error estimates for a Galerkin discretization of a pure-Lagrangian formulation are obtained, that are written in terms of the projections built in [10] and [11]. In [4] and [5] a pure-Lagrangian formulation has been used for more general problems. Specifically, we have considered a (possibly degenerate) variable coefficient diffusive term instead of the simpler Laplacian, general mixed Dirichlet-Robin boundary conditions, and a time dependent domain. Moreover, we have analyzed a scheme with approximate characteristic curves and presented numerical results for pure-Lagrangian and semi-Lagrangian methods. In [6] a unified approach to state pure-Lagrangian and semi-Lagrangian methods for solving scalar linear convection-diffusion partial differential equations is introduced. More precisely, a quite general change of variable from the current

[†]Departamento de Matemáticas, Universidade da Coruña, c/ Mendizábal s/n, 15403 Ferrol, Spain (marta.benitez@udc.es)

[‡]Departamento de Matemática Aplicada, Universidade de Santiago de Compostela, c/ Lope Gómez de Marzoa s/n, 15786 Santiago de Compostela, Spain (alfredo.bermudez@usc.es)

configuration to a reference configuration is proposed obtaining a new strong formulation of the problem from which classical and new time discretization methods can be introduced in a natural way. Moreover, new stability estimates for the pure-Lagrangian method proposed in [4] and [5] have been obtained. More precisely, an $l^\infty(H^1)$ -stability estimate independent of the diffusion coefficient has been proved. Besides, if the underlying flow is incompressible, a stability inequality independent of the final time has been shown.

By applying the above ideas to the Navier-Stokes equations, we can obtain displacement methods similar to those used for numerical solution of solid mechanics problems. More precisely, in [2] a unified formulation to introduce Lagrangian and semi-Lagrangian velocity and displacement methods for solving the Navier-Stokes equations is proposed. By using this formulation, two new second-order characteristics methods in terms of the displacement and classical second-order characteristics methods in terms of the velocity are obtained. Moreover, numerical results showing the performance of the obtained numerical methods are presented.

In this paper, we consider the coupling of a viscous Newtonian incompressible fluid and a linear elastic solid. The governing equations for the fluid are the unsteady incompressible Navier-Stokes equations and, for the solid, the Navier-Lamé equations of linear elastodynamics. These equations are coupled by the standard kinematic and kinetic interface conditions, namely, continuity of displacements and forces across the interface. We propose a second-order pure-Lagrangian method combined with finite element approximations for the numerical solution of this problem. For this purpose, we use the mathematical formalism of continuum mechanics (see for instance [16]) following the ideas given in [4] and [2]. More precisely, the Navier-Stokes equations and the Navier-Lamé equations are written in material coordinates and in terms of displacements and fluid pressure. It is remarkable that the interface kinematic condition is included in the definition of the functional space where the numerical solution is looked for.

The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 a general initial and boundary value problem is posed in a time dependent bounded domain and some hypotheses and notations concerning motions are stated. In Section 3, a change of variable from the current configuration to an initial configuration is proposed obtaining a new strong formulation of the problem in a time-independent domain. More precisely, the fluid-structure interaction problem is written in Lagrangian coordinates and in terms of displacements and fluid pressure. Then, the standard associated weak problem is obtained. In Section 4, we propose a second-order time discretization scheme for solving the coupled weak formulation. Section 5 discusses the fully discretized scheme using finite element methods: in the solid, continuous piecewise linear functions for each component of the displacement field and, in the fluid, the same approximation for the pressure and the mini-element (P_1 -bubble) for the displacement field. Moreover, we obtain approximations of velocity and pressure in Eulerian coordinates by using the approximations of displacement and pressure in Lagrangian coordinates. A method to re-initialize the pure Lagrange-Galerkin method is presented in Section 6. Finally, in Section 7 numerical examples are shown.

2. Statement of the problem. General assumptions and notations. Let Ω be a bounded domain in $\mathbb{R}^d$ ($d = 2, 3$) with Lipschitz boundary Γ . Let us assume that Ω and Γ are divided into two parts: $\Omega = \text{int}(\overline{\Omega}^f \cup \overline{\Omega}^s)$ and $\Gamma = \Gamma^D \cup \Gamma^N$, with $\Gamma^D \cap \Gamma^N = \emptyset$. We call $\Gamma^f = \overline{\Omega}^f \cap \overline{\Omega}^s$. Let $X : \overline{\Omega} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ be a *motion* in the sense of Gurtin [16]. In particular, $X \in \mathbf{C}^3(\overline{\Omega} \times \mathbb{R})$ and for each fixed $t \in \mathbb{R}$, $X(\cdot, t)$ is a one-to-one function satisfying

$$\det F(p, t) > 0 \quad \forall p \in \overline{\Omega}, \quad (2.1)$$

being $F(\cdot, t) = \nabla_p X(\cdot, t)$ the *deformation gradient* of $X(\cdot, t)$. For given $\mathcal{A} \subset \overline{\Omega}$, we call $\mathcal{A}_t = X(\mathcal{A}, t)$. In practice, a bounded time interval is considered for the motion, namely, $[t_0, T]$, being t_0, T two non-negative numbers. For simplicity, in this paper we assume that $X(p, t_0) = p \quad \forall p \in \overline{\Omega}$. Notice that in many cases the body is at rest until the initial time, i.e., $X(p, t) = p \quad \forall t \leq t_0 \quad \forall p \in \overline{\Omega}$ and then the initial velocity is null. Let us introduce the following *trajectories* of the motion

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T}^f &:= \{(x, t) : x \in \overline{\Omega}_t^f, t \in [t_0, T]\}, \\ \mathcal{T} &:= \{(x, t) : x \in \overline{\Omega}_t, t \in [t_0, T]\}. \end{aligned}$$

For each t , $X(\cdot, t)$ is a one-to-one mapping from $\overline{\Omega}$ onto $\overline{\Omega}_t$; hence it has an inverse

$$P(\cdot, t) : \overline{\Omega}_t \rightarrow \overline{\Omega}, \quad (2.2)$$

such that

$$X(P(x, t), t) = x, \quad P(X(p, t), t) = p \quad \forall (x, t) \in \mathcal{T} \quad \forall (p, t) \in \bar{\Omega} \times [t_0, T]. \quad (2.3)$$

The mapping $P : \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \bar{\Omega}$ is called the *reference map* of motion X and $P \in \mathbf{C}^3(\mathcal{T})$ (see [16], pp. 65–66). For given $t_0 \leq \tau \leq T$, motion X can also be defined relative to the configuration at time τ . It is the mapping

$$X_\tau : \bar{\Omega}_\tau \times [t_0, T] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d,$$

given by

$$X_\tau(y, t) := X(P(y, \tau), t) \quad \forall (y, t) \in \bar{\Omega}_\tau \times [t_0, T]. \quad (2.4)$$

Thus, mapping $t \in (t_0, T) \rightarrow X_\tau(y, t)$ represents the trajectory described by the material point that is at position y at time τ . Moreover, we notice that $x = X_\tau(y, t)$ if and only if $y = X_t(x, \tau)$. Let us introduce the notation

$$F_\tau(y, t) := \text{grad}_y X_\tau(y, t). \quad (2.5)$$

Remark 2.1. For the sake of clarity in the notation, in expressions involving gradients and time derivatives we use the following notation (see, for instance, [16]):

(i) We denote by p the *material points* in $\bar{\Omega}$, by t the *current time*, by x the *spatial points* in $\bar{\Omega}_t$ and by y the points in $\bar{\Omega}_\tau$ with $t_0 < \tau \leq T$.

(ii) A *material field* is a mapping with domain $\bar{\Omega} \times [t_0, T]$ and a *spatial field* is a mapping with domain $\mathcal{T}$.

(iii) If Φ is a smooth material field, we denote by $\nabla\Phi$ (respectively, by $\text{Div}\Phi$) the gradient (respectively, the divergence) with respect to the first argument, and by $\dot{\Phi}$ the partial derivative with respect to the second argument (time).

(iv) If Ψ is a smooth spatial field, we denote by $\text{grad}\Psi$ (respectively, $\text{div}\Psi$) the gradient (respectively, the divergence) with respect to the first argument, and by Ψ' the partial derivative with respect to the second argument (time). Moreover, $\dot{\Psi}$ denotes the material time derivative with respect to time, that is

$$\dot{\Psi}(x, t) = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\Psi(X(p, t), t))|_{p=P(x, t)} \quad \forall (x, t) \in \mathcal{T}.$$

FIG. 2.1. Functions referred to configuration at time τ , $t_0 \leq \tau \leq T$.

If Ψ is a spatial field, we introduce the field Ψ_τ defined in $\bar{\Omega}_\tau \times [t_0, T]$ by

$$\Psi_\tau(y, t) := \Psi(X_\tau(y, t), t) \quad \forall (y, t) \in \bar{\Omega}_\tau \times [t_0, T]. \quad (2.6)$$

These functions are depicted in Figure 2.1. Notice that for $\tau = t$

$$\Psi_t(x, t) := \Psi(X_t(x, t), t) = \Psi(X(P(x, t), t), t) = \Psi(x, t).$$

For $\tau = t_0$, Ψ_{t_0} is the *material description* of Ψ also denoted by Ψ_m . Let us introduce the displacement field relative to the configuration at time τ , that is,

$$\mathbf{u}_\tau(y, t) := X_\tau(y, t) - y \quad \forall (y, t) \in \overline{\Omega}_\tau \times [t_0, T]. \quad (2.7)$$

For $\tau = t_0$, $\mathbf{u}_{t_0}$ is also denoted by $\mathbf{u}$. Let us recall that the *spatial description* of the velocity $\mathbf{v} : \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ is defined by

$$\mathbf{v}(x, t) := \dot{X}(P(x, t), t) \quad \forall (x, t) \in \mathcal{T}. \quad (2.8)$$

Let us consider the following general initial-boundary value problem (motion equation of continuum mechanics):

(GSP) General Strong Problem. *Find two functions $\mathbf{v} : \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ and $T : \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \text{Lin}$ such that*

$$\rho(x, t)\mathbf{v}'(x, t) + \rho(x, t) \text{grad } \mathbf{v}(x, t)\mathbf{v}(x, t) - \text{div } T(x, t) = \mathbf{b}(x, t) \text{ in } \mathcal{T}, \quad (2.9)$$

subject to the boundary conditions

$$\mathbf{v}(x, t) = \mathbf{v}_D(x, t) \text{ on } \Gamma_t^D, \quad (2.10)$$

$$T(x, t)\mathbf{n}(x, t) = \mathbf{h}(x, t) \text{ on } \Gamma_t^N, \quad (2.11)$$

for $t \in (t_0, T)$, and to the initial condition

$$\mathbf{v}(x, t_0) = \mathbf{v}^0(x) \text{ in } \overline{\Omega}. \quad (2.12)$$

In the above equations, *Lin* denotes the space of tensors in the d -dimensional space, $\rho : \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $\mathbf{b} : \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$, $\mathbf{v}_D(\cdot, t) : \Gamma_t^D \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ and $\mathbf{h}(\cdot, t) : \Gamma_t^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$, $t \in (t_0, T)$, are given spatial fields, $\mathbf{n}(\cdot, t)$ is the outward unit normal vector to Γ_t . Notice that the system of equations given in **(GSP)** is undetermined. In Section 3, in order to complete the system, constitutive assumptions on the form of the stress tensor will be introduced. These additional equations depend on the behavior of the materials. Moreover, we notice that equations (2.9)-(2.11) are expressed in spatial coordinates, $x = X(p, t)$, which belong, in general, to an unknown domain. In order to avoid this difficulty we will rewrite problem **(GSP)** in configuration $\overline{\Omega}$ which is supposed to be given. In the following, $\mathcal{A}$ denotes a bounded domain in $\mathbb{R}^d$. Let us recall the definition of the Hilbert spaces $H^1(\mathcal{A})$ and $L^2(\mathcal{A})$:

$$L^2(\mathcal{A}) = \left\{ f : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \text{ measurable, } \int_{\Omega} f^2 dx < \infty \right\}, \quad (2.13)$$

$$H^1(\mathcal{A}) = \left\{ f : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \text{ measurable, } f, \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_i} \in L^2(\mathcal{A}), i = 1, \dots, d \right\}. \quad (2.14)$$

We also introduce the notation $\mathbf{H}^1(\mathcal{A}) = (H^1(\mathcal{A}))^d$ and denote by $\mathbf{H}_{\Gamma^P}^1(\mathcal{A})$ the closed subspace of $\mathbf{H}^1(\mathcal{A})$ defined by

$$\mathbf{H}_{\Gamma^P}^1(\mathcal{A}) := \{ \mathbf{w} \in \mathbf{H}^1(\mathcal{A}), \mathbf{w}|_{\Gamma^P} \equiv 0 \}, \quad (2.15)$$

where Γ^P is a part of the boundary of $\mathcal{A}$ of non-null measure.

3. Strong problem and weak formulation in Lagrangian coordinates. We are going to develop some formal computations in order to write the above problem **(GSP)** in Lagrangian coordinates and in terms of displacement. Firstly, from the definition of the material time derivative and by using the chain rule, we get (see, for instance, [16])

$$\dot{\mathbf{v}}(x, t) = \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t}(x, t) + \text{grad}_x \mathbf{v}(x, t)\mathbf{v}(x, t) = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{v}_m(p, t)|_{p=P(x, t)} \quad \forall (x, t) \in \mathcal{T}. \quad (3.1)$$

Notice that we have

$$\mathbf{v}_m(p, t) = \dot{X}(p, t) = \dot{\mathbf{u}}(p, t), \quad (3.2)$$

for $(p, t) \in \overline{\Omega} \times [t_0, T]$. Then, from (3.1) and (3.2), we deduce

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t}(x, t) + \text{grad}_x \mathbf{v}(x, t) \mathbf{v}(x, t) = \ddot{\mathbf{u}}(p, t)|_{p=P(x, t)} \quad \forall (x, t) \in \mathcal{T}. \quad (3.3)$$

Then, by evaluating equation (2.9) at point $x = X(p, t)$ and then using (3.3), we obtain

$$\rho(X(p, t), t) \ddot{\mathbf{u}}(p, t) - \text{div}_x T(X(p, t), t) = \mathbf{b}(X(p, t), t), \quad (3.4)$$

for $(p, t) \in \Omega \times (t_0, T)$. Notice that in (3.4) there are derivatives with respect to the Eulerian variable x . In order to write a strong formulation of problem **(GSP)** in Lagrangian coordinates we can use the divergence theorem, the change of variable $x = X(p, t)$, the chain rule and the localization theorem, to obtain the equality

$$-\text{div}_x T(X(p, t), t) = -\text{Div}_p (T_m(p, t) \det F(p, t) F^{-t}(p, t)) \frac{1}{\det F(p, t)}, \quad (3.5)$$

for $(p, t) \in \Omega \times (t_0, T)$. Then, (3.4) becomes

$$\rho_m(p, t) \ddot{\mathbf{u}}(p, t) - \frac{1}{\det F(p, t)} \text{Div}_p (T_m(p, t) \det F(p, t) F^{-t}(p, t)) = \mathbf{b}_m(p, t), \quad (3.6)$$

for $(p, t) \in \Omega \times (t_0, T)$. Next, by evaluating equations (2.10) and (2.11) at point $x = X(p, t)$ and using (3.2) and (2.12), we obtain the following material versions of the boundary and initial conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{u}}(p, t) &= (\mathbf{v}_D)_m(p, t) \text{ on } \Gamma^D \times (t_0, T), \\ T_m(p, t) F^{-t}(p, t) \mathbf{m}(p) &= |F^{-t}(p, t) \mathbf{m}(p)| \mathbf{h}_m(p, t) \text{ on } \Gamma^N \times (t_0, T), \\ \dot{\mathbf{u}}(p, t_0) &= \mathbf{v}^0(p) \text{ in } \overline{\Omega}, \end{aligned}$$

being $\mathbf{m}(p)$ the outward unit normal vector to Γ at point p , and where we have used that

$$\mathbf{n}(X(p, t), t) = \frac{F^{-t}(p, t) \mathbf{m}(p)}{|F^{-t}(p, t) \mathbf{m}(p)|} \quad (p, t) \in \Gamma \times (t_0, T).$$

As a consequence of these results, the equations of problem **(GSP)** in the deformed configuration are transformed into equations in configuration $\overline{\Omega}$. More precisely, we have got the following formulation in $\Omega \times (t_0, T)$:

(LGSP) Lagrangian General Strong Problem. *Find two functions $\mathbf{u} : \overline{\Omega} \times [t_0, T] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ and $T_m : \overline{\Omega} \times [t_0, T] \rightarrow \text{Lin}$ such that*

$$\rho_m(p, t) \ddot{\mathbf{u}}(p, t) - \frac{1}{\det F(p, t)} \text{Div} (T_m(p, t) \det F(p, t) F^{-t}(p, t)) = \mathbf{b}_m(p, t), \quad (3.7)$$

for $(p, t) \in \Omega \times (t_0, T)$, subject to the boundary conditions

$$\dot{\mathbf{u}}(p, t) = (\mathbf{v}_D)_m(p, t) \text{ on } \Gamma^D \times (t_0, T), \quad (3.8)$$

$$T_m(p, t) F^{-t}(p, t) \mathbf{m}(p) = |F^{-t}(p, t) \mathbf{m}(p)| \mathbf{h}_m(p, t) \text{ on } \Gamma^N \times (t_0, T), \quad (3.9)$$

and to the initial condition

$$\dot{\mathbf{u}}(p, t_0) = \mathbf{v}^0(p) \text{ in } \overline{\Omega}. \quad (3.10)$$

Although the numerical method could be written for a more general case, for simplicity of presentation, we are going to consider two specific types of materials in domain Ω . More precisely, at each instant $t \in [t_0, T]$, let us consider an incompressible Newtonian fluid occupying domain Ω_t^f and a homogeneous isotropic linear elastic material occupying domain Ω_t^s . Moreover, let us assume, for the sake of simplicity, that the residual stress $T(p, t_0) = \mathbf{0} \quad \forall p \in \Omega^s$. Next, we introduce constitutive equations for these types of materials.

- For an incompressible Newtonian fluid, the Cauchy stress tensor T has the following form:

$$T(x, t) = -\pi(x, t)I + \eta(\operatorname{grad} \mathbf{v}(x, t) + \operatorname{grad} \mathbf{v}^t(x, t)), \quad (3.11)$$

for $(x, t) \in \mathcal{T}^f$. In the above equation, $\pi : \mathcal{T}^f \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ denotes the pressure (unknown) and η the dynamic viscosity (known). Thus, the equation of motion (3.7) must be supplemented by the constitutive equation (3.11) and the incompressibility condition

$$\operatorname{div} \mathbf{v}(x, t) = 0, \quad (3.12)$$

for $(x, t) \in \mathcal{T}^f$.

- For a homogeneous isotropic linear elastic material, *the first Piola-Kirchoff stress tensor*:

$$T_m(p, t) \det F(p, t) F^{-t}(p, t),$$

is related with displacement by the approximate equality (see, for instance, [16])

$$T_m(p, t) \det F(p, t) F^{-t}(p, t) \simeq \lambda \operatorname{Div} \mathbf{u}(p, t) I + 2\mu \mathcal{E}(\mathbf{u})(p, t) \quad \forall (p, t) \in \Omega^s \times (t_0, T), \quad (3.13)$$

where λ and μ are the Lamé coefficients and $\mathcal{E}(\mathbf{u})(p, t) = 1/2 (\nabla \mathbf{u}(p, t) + \nabla \mathbf{u}^t(p, t))$ is the *infinitesimal strain tensor*. Let us recall that the Lamé coefficients can be written in terms of Young modulus E and Poisson ratio ν as follows:

$$\mu = \frac{E}{2(1+\nu)}, \quad \lambda = \frac{E\nu}{(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)}.$$

Similar to the equation of motion, we are going to write equations (3.11) and (3.12) in Lagrangian coordinates. Firstly, by using the chain rule, we obtain (see, for instance, [16])

$$\begin{aligned} \operatorname{div}_x \mathbf{v}(X(p, t), t) &= \operatorname{tr}(\operatorname{grad}_x \mathbf{v}(X(p, t), t)) = \operatorname{tr}(\nabla \dot{\mathbf{u}}(p, t) F^{-1}(p, t)) \\ &= \nabla \dot{\mathbf{u}}(p, t) F^{-1}(p, t) \cdot I = \nabla \dot{\mathbf{u}}(p, t) \cdot F^{-t}(p, t) \quad \forall (p, t) \in \Omega^f \times (t_0, T). \end{aligned} \quad (3.14)$$

Next, by evaluating equations (3.11) and (3.12) at point $x = X(p, t)$, using the chain rule in (3.11) and equality (3.14), we get

$$T_m(p, t) = -\pi_m(p, t)I + \eta \left(\nabla \dot{\mathbf{u}}(p, t) F^{-1}(p, t) + F^{-t}(p, t) (\nabla \dot{\mathbf{u}})^t(p, t) \right), \quad (3.15)$$

$$\nabla \dot{\mathbf{u}}(p, t) \cdot F^{-t}(p, t) = 0, \quad (3.16)$$

for $(p, t) \in \Omega^f \times (t_0, T)$. Let us introduce equations (3.13), (3.15) and (3.16) in the above problem (**LGSP**). Then, we have the following fluid-structure interaction problem written in the reference configuration:

(LFSP) Lagrangian fluid-structure interaction problem. *Find two functions $\mathbf{u} : \bar{\Omega} \times [t_0, T] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ and $\pi_m : \bar{\Omega}^f \times [t_0, T] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that*

$$\rho_m(p, t) \ddot{\mathbf{u}}(p, t) - \frac{1}{\det F(p, t)} \operatorname{Div} (T_m(p, t) \det F(p, t) F^{-t}(p, t)) = \mathbf{b}_m(p, t) \quad \forall (p, t) \in \Omega \times (t_0, T), \quad (3.17)$$

$$T_m(p, t) = -\pi_m(p, t)I + \eta \left(\nabla \dot{\mathbf{u}}(p, t) F^{-1}(p, t) + F^{-t}(p, t) (\nabla \dot{\mathbf{u}})^t(p, t) \right) \quad \forall (p, t) \in \Omega^f \times (t_0, T), \quad (3.18)$$

$$\nabla \dot{\mathbf{u}}(p, t) \cdot F^{-t}(p, t) = 0 \quad \forall (p, t) \in \Omega^f \times (t_0, T), \quad (3.19)$$

$$T_m(p, t) \det F(p, t) F^{-t}(p, t) = \lambda \operatorname{Div} \mathbf{u}(p, t) I + 2\mu \mathcal{E}(\mathbf{u})(p, t) \quad \forall (p, t) \in \Omega^s \times (t_0, T), \quad (3.20)$$

subject to the boundary conditions

$$\dot{\mathbf{u}}(p, t) = (\mathbf{v}_D)_m(p, t) \quad \text{on } \Gamma^D \times (t_0, T), \quad (3.21)$$

$$T_m(p, t) F^{-t}(p, t) \mathbf{m}(p) = |F^{-t}(p, t) \mathbf{m}(p)| \mathbf{h}_m(p, t) \quad \text{on } \Gamma^N \times (t_0, T), \quad (3.22)$$

and to the initial condition

$$\dot{\mathbf{u}}(p, t_0) = \mathbf{v}^0(p) \quad \text{in } \bar{\Omega}. \quad (3.23)$$

Now, by multiplying equation (3.17) by $\det F$ and by a test function $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbf{H}_{\Gamma_D}^1(\Omega)$, integrating in Ω , applying the usual Green's formula and equations (3.18), (3.20) and (3.22) we easily get a weak formulation for the motion equation. Similarly, by multiplying equation (3.19) by $\det F$ and by a test function $q \in L^2(\Omega^f)$ and integrating in Ω^f we obtain a weak formulation for the incompressibility equation in the fluid. The whole problem is the following:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\Omega} \rho_m(p, t) \det F(p, t) \ddot{\mathbf{u}}(p, t) \cdot \mathbf{z}(p) dp - \int_{\Omega^f} \pi_m(p, t) \det F(p, t) F^{-t}(p, t) \cdot \nabla \mathbf{z}(p) dp \\ & + \eta \int_{\Omega^f} \left(\nabla \dot{\mathbf{u}}(p, t) F^{-1}(p, t) + F^{-t}(p, t) (\nabla \dot{\mathbf{u}})^t(p, t) \right) \det F(p, t) F^{-t}(p, t) \cdot \nabla \mathbf{z}(p) dp \\ & \quad + \lambda \int_{\Omega^s} \text{Div } \mathbf{u}(p, t) \text{Div } \mathbf{z}(p) dp + 2\mu \int_{\Omega^s} \mathcal{E}(\mathbf{u})(p, t) \cdot \mathcal{E}(\mathbf{z})(p) dp \\ & = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{b}_m(p, t) \cdot \mathbf{z}(p) \det F(p, t) dp + \int_{\Gamma^N} |F^{-t}(p, t) \mathbf{m}(p)| \det F(p, t) \mathbf{h}_m(p, t) \cdot \mathbf{z}(p) dA_p, \end{aligned} \quad (3.24)$$

$$\int_{\Omega^f} \det F(p, t) \nabla \dot{\mathbf{u}}(p, t) \cdot F^{-t}(p, t) q(p) dp = 0, \quad (3.25)$$

$\forall \mathbf{z} \in \mathbf{H}_{\Gamma_D}^1(\Omega)$, $\forall q \in L^2(\Omega^f)$ and $t \in (t_0, T)$. These are formal computations, i.e., we have assumed appropriate regularity of the involved data and solution. Notice that the above problem is non-linear in the fluid but not in the solid. However, extension of what follows to nonlinear solids is straightforward.

Numerical methods formulated in material coordinates are called pure-Lagrangian methods. Thus, from (3.24)-(3.25), we can obtain different pure-Lagrangian numerical methods. These methods are useful, in particular, for solving free surface problems because the computational domain is independent of time.

Remark 3.1. Notice that in equations (3.24)-(3.25), the integrals corresponding to the fluid can also be written in terms of the velocity instead of the displacement, by replacing $\dot{\mathbf{u}}$ with $\mathbf{v}_m$. Thus, from (3.24)-(3.25) we can obtain pure-Lagrangian methods whose unknowns are either the fluid velocity, the fluid pressure and the solid displacement or the fluid and solid displacements and the fluid pressure. We will call displacement methods to those written in terms of the fluid and solid displacements and the fluid pressure. In this paper, we propose a second-order pure-Lagrangian displacement method. As we can see in Section 5, displacement methods are useful for solving fluid-structure interaction problems because fluid-solid coupling at the interface is straightforward. More precisely, continuity of displacements across the interface is included in the definition of the function space where the numerical solution is looked for (*essential condition*), while the kinetic condition (continuity of force) is involved in the weak formulation (i.e., it is a *natural condition*).

4. Time discretization. Depending on the differentiation formulas used to approximate the time derivatives and on the numerical formulas used to approximate the other terms, we can obtain, from (3.24)-(3.25), different pure-Lagrangian methods. In this section, we introduce a Newmark-like second-order centered scheme for time semi-discretization of (3.24)-(3.25).

The following notations will be used in the rest of the paper. Let us denote the number of time steps by N , the time step $\Delta t = (T - t_0)/N$, and the mesh-points $t_n = t_0 + n\Delta t$. We will use the notation $\Psi^l(y) := \Psi(y, t_l)$ for a function $\Psi(y, t)$. Similarly, for a given material field Φ (respectively, a spatial field Ψ) we will denote by $\Phi_{\Delta t}^l$ (respectively, $\Psi_{m, \Delta t}^l$) approximations of Φ^l (respectively, Ψ_m^l) obtained with a time-semidiscretized scheme.

In order to discretize the time derivatives $\ddot{\mathbf{u}}$ and $\dot{\mathbf{u}}$ in equations (3.24)-(3.25), we propose the following second-order centered formulas:

- Three-point second-order centered formula:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \Psi}{\partial t^2}(y, t) = \frac{\Psi(y, t + \Delta t) - 2\Psi(y, t) + \Psi(y, t - \Delta t)}{\Delta t^2} + O(\Delta t^2). \quad (4.1)$$

- Two-point second-order centered formula:

$$\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial t}(y, t) = \frac{\Psi(y, t + \Delta t) - \Psi(y, t - \Delta t)}{2\Delta t} + O(\Delta t^2). \quad (4.2)$$

Moreover, the following formula will be convenient to approximate the gradient of the solid displacement:

- Two-point second-order centered formula:

$$\text{grad } \Psi(y, t) = \frac{\text{grad } \Psi(y, t + \Delta t) + \text{grad } \Psi(y, t - \Delta t)}{2} + O(\Delta t^2). \quad (4.3)$$

The above equalities are obtained in a standard way by assuming appropriate regularity of the involved data and using Taylor expansions. Then, by evaluating (3.24) and (3.25) at time $t = t_{n+1/2}$ and then using second-order formulas (4.1), (4.2) and (4.3) for $\Psi = \mathbf{u}$, we deduce the following Newmark-like time-semidiscretized scheme:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\Omega} \rho^{n+1/2} \circ X_{\Delta t}^{n+1/2} \det F_{\Delta t}^{n+1/2} \frac{\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{n+3/2} - 2\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{n+1/2} + \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{n-1/2}}{\Delta t^2} \cdot \mathbf{z} dp \\ & \quad - \int_{\Omega^f} \pi_{m, \Delta t}^{n+1/2} \det F_{\Delta t}^{n+1/2} (F_{\Delta t}^{n+1/2})^{-t} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{z} dp \\ & + \eta \int_{\Omega^f} \det F_{\Delta t}^{n+1/2} \frac{\nabla \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{n+3/2} - \nabla \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{n-1/2}}{2\Delta t} (F_{\Delta t}^{n+1/2})^{-1} (F_{\Delta t}^{n+1/2})^{-t} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{z} dp \\ & + \eta \int_{\Omega^f} \det F_{\Delta t}^{n+1/2} (F_{\Delta t}^{n+1/2})^{-t} \frac{(\nabla \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{n+3/2})^t - (\nabla \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{n-1/2})^t}{2\Delta t} (F_{\Delta t}^{n+1/2})^{-t} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{z} dp \\ & + \frac{\lambda}{2} \int_{\Omega^s} \left(\text{Div } \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{n+3/2} + \text{Div } \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{n-1/2} \right) \text{Div } \mathbf{z} dp + \mu \int_{\Omega^s} \left(\mathcal{E}(\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{n+3/2}) + \mathcal{E}(\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{n-1/2}) \right) \cdot \mathcal{E}(\mathbf{z}) dp \\ = & \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{b}^{n+1/2} \circ X_{\Delta t}^{n+1/2} \cdot \mathbf{z} \det F_{\Delta t}^{n+1/2} dp + \int_{\Gamma^N} |(F_{\Delta t}^{n+1/2})^{-t} \mathbf{m}| \det F_{\Delta t}^{n+1/2} \mathbf{h}^{n+1/2} \circ X_{\Delta t}^{n+1/2} \cdot \mathbf{z} dA_p, \quad (4.4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\int_{\Omega^f} \det F_{\Delta t}^{n+1/2} \frac{\nabla \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{n+3/2} - \nabla \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{n-1/2}}{2\Delta t} \cdot (F_{\Delta t}^{n+1/2})^{-t} q dp = 0, \quad (4.5)$$

$\forall \mathbf{z} \in \mathbf{H}_{\Gamma^D}^1(\Omega)$, $\forall q \in L^2(\Omega^f)$ and $0 \leq n \leq N-1$. Notice that X and F appearing in equations (3.24) and (3.25) are unknowns. However, they can be easily approximated from $\mathbf{u}$ by using the following equalities:

$$\begin{aligned} X(p, t) &= p + \mathbf{u}(p, t), \\ F(p, t) &= \nabla X(p, t) = I + \nabla \mathbf{u}(p, t), \end{aligned}$$

for $(p, t) \in \Omega \times (t_0, T)$. More precisely, in the above pure-Lagrangian problem we have used the following approximations of $X^{n+1/2}$ and $F^{n+1/2}$

$$\begin{aligned} X_{\Delta t}^{n+1/2}(p) &:= p + \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{n+1/2}(p), \\ F_{\Delta t}^{n+1/2}(p) &:= I + \nabla \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{n+1/2}(p), \end{aligned}$$

for $p \in \Omega$ and $0 \leq n \leq N-1$. Notice that while the continuous problem is non-linear, *the implicit semi-discrete scheme (4.4)-(4.5) is linear* in the two unknowns $\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{n+3/2}$ and $\pi_{m, \Delta t}^{n+1/2}$. Moreover, we emphasize that the consistency error is of order two.

Remark 4.1. Let us observe that the initial condition $\mathbf{u}^{1/2}$ appearing in the above scheme (4.4)-(4.5) is unknown but it can be approximated by using the initial condition for the continuous problem (3.23). More precisely, by using the following Taylor expansions satisfied by a smooth enough displacement field

$$\mathbf{u}(p, t - \Delta t/2) = \mathbf{u}(p, t) - \mathbf{v}_m(p, t) \frac{\Delta t}{2} + \dot{\mathbf{v}}(X(p, t), t) \frac{\Delta t^2}{8} + O(\Delta t^3), \quad (4.6)$$

$$\mathbf{u}(p, t + \Delta t/2) = \mathbf{u}(p, t) + \mathbf{v}_m(p, t) \frac{\Delta t}{2} + \dot{\mathbf{v}}(X(p, t), t) \frac{\Delta t^2}{8} + O(\Delta t^3), \quad (4.7)$$

we deduce the following third-order approximation of $\mathbf{u}^{1/2}$

$$\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{1/2}(p) := \mathbf{u}^{-1/2}(p) + \mathbf{v}^0(p) \Delta t \quad \forall p \in \overline{\Omega}. \quad (4.8)$$

For simplicity, in this paper we have assumed that initial velocity $\mathbf{v}^0$ is null so we take

$$\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{-1/2}(p) = \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{1/2}(p) = \mathbf{0} \quad \forall p \in \overline{\Omega}. \quad (4.9)$$

Otherwise, it is convenient to write the considered problem in configuration $\overline{\Omega}_{t_0-\Delta t/2}$ instead of $\overline{\Omega}$ noting that $\mathbf{u}_{t_0-\Delta t/2}^{-1/2} \equiv \mathbf{0}$ (see [2] for details). In the academic test examples considered in this paper, the initial velocity is not null but we know and use the exact value of $\mathbf{u}^{-1/2}$. We have observed quite surprisingly that if we start with a third order approximation of $\mathbf{u}^{1/2}$ as (4.8), then the above method is also second-order accurate for the velocity. In order to understand the reason of this fact, we are going to analyze the following simple scheme

$$\frac{\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{n+3/2}(p) - 2\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{n+1/2}(p) + \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{n-1/2}(p)}{\Delta t^2} = \ddot{\mathbf{u}}^{n+1/2}(p), \quad (4.10)$$

for $p \in \overline{\Omega}$ and $0 \leq n \leq N-1$. If $\mathbf{u}$ is smooth enough, we have

$$\frac{\mathbf{u}^{n+3/2}(p) - 2\mathbf{u}^{n+1/2}(p) + \mathbf{u}^{n-1/2}(p)}{\Delta t^2} = \ddot{\mathbf{u}}^{n+1/2}(p) + O(\Delta t^2), \quad (4.11)$$

for $p \in \overline{\Omega}$ and $0 \leq n \leq N-1$. Then, from (4.10) and (4.11) we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{n+3/2}(p) - \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{n+1/2}(p)}{\Delta t^2} - \frac{\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{n+1/2}(p) - \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{n-1/2}(p)}{\Delta t^2} \\ &= \frac{\mathbf{u}^{n+3/2}(p) - \mathbf{u}^{n+1/2}(p)}{\Delta t^2} - \frac{\mathbf{u}^{n+1/2}(p) - \mathbf{u}^{n-1/2}(p)}{\Delta t^2} + O(\Delta t^2), \end{aligned} \quad (4.12)$$

for $p \in \overline{\Omega}$ and $0 \leq n \leq N-1$. Now, for fixed q , $0 \leq q \leq N-1$, let us sum (4.12) multiplied by Δt from $n=0$ to $n=q$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{q+3/2}(p) - \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{q+1/2}(p)}{\Delta t} - \frac{\mathbf{u}^{q+3/2}(p) - \mathbf{u}^{q+1/2}(p)}{\Delta t} \\ &= \frac{\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{1/2}(p) - \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{-1/2}(p)}{\Delta t} - \frac{\mathbf{u}^{1/2}(p) - \mathbf{u}^{-1/2}(p)}{\Delta t} + O(\Delta t^2) \quad \forall p \in \overline{\Omega}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.13)$$

Next, by subtracting (4.6) from (4.7) for $t = t_{q+1}$ and then using the result in (4.13), we obtain

$$\frac{\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{q+3/2}(p) - \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{q+1/2}(p)}{\Delta t} - (\mathbf{v}_m)^{q+1}(p) = \frac{\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{1/2}(p) - \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{-1/2}(p)}{\Delta t} - \frac{\mathbf{u}^{1/2}(p) - \mathbf{u}^{-1/2}(p)}{\Delta t} + O(\Delta t^2), \quad (4.14)$$

for $0 \leq q \leq N-1$ and $p \in \overline{\Omega}$. Now, from this equality we deduce that, for the simple scheme (4.10), a second-order approximation of the material velocity is obtained if the initial conditions satisfy

$$\frac{\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{1/2}(p) - \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{-1/2}(p)}{\Delta t} - \frac{\mathbf{u}^{1/2}(p) - \mathbf{u}^{-1/2}(p)}{\Delta t} = O(\Delta t^2) \quad \forall p \in \overline{\Omega}. \quad (4.15)$$

Therefore, for scheme (4.4)-(4.5) a second-order approximation for the velocity is obtained when we start with $\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{-1/2} = \mathbf{u}^{-1/2}$ and $\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{1/2}$ given in (4.8). Notice that if the displacement field is smooth enough, these initial conditions satisfy (4.15).

Remark 4.2. By using analogous procedures to the ones in Remark 4.1, we can obtain approximate Dirichlet boundary conditions for the displacement. More precisely, by using that

$$\mathbf{u}^{n+3/2}(p) = \mathbf{u}^{n-1/2}(p) + 2\Delta t \mathbf{v}^{n+1/2}(X(p, t_{n+1/2})) + O(\Delta t^3),$$

we deduce the following Dirichlet boundary condition for $\mathbf{u}^{n+3/2}$ preserving the second order of the global scheme:

$$\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{n+3/2}(p) = \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t}^{n-1/2}(p) + 2\Delta t \mathbf{v}_D^{n+1/2}(X_{\Delta t}^{n+1/2}(p)),$$

for $p \in \Gamma^D$ and $0 \leq n \leq N-1$.

5. Space discretization. Finite element method. In this section we propose a space discretization of the time semidiscretized problem (4.4)-(4.5) by using finite elements. More precisely, we consider continuous piecewise-linear for each solid displacement component and for the fluid the *mini-element* (see [1]), that is, continuous piecewise-linear+bubble finite element for each fluid displacement component and continuous piecewise-linear for pressure. In what follows, for a given material field Φ (respectively, a spatial field Ψ) we will denote by $\Phi_{\Delta t, h}^l$ (respectively, $\Psi_{m, \Delta t, h}^l$) approximations of Φ^l (respectively, Ψ_m^l) obtained with a fully discretized scheme, being h the meshsize.

Let us suppose Ω^f and Ω^s are two bounded domains in $\mathbb{R}^d$ with Lipschitz polygonal boundaries. Let us consider two suitable families of regular triangulations of $\overline{\Omega}^f$ and $\overline{\Omega}^s$ to be denoted by $\mathfrak{T}_h^f$ and $\mathfrak{T}_h^s$ respectively, both consisting of elements K of diameter $\leq h$. Moreover, let us assume they are compatible with the partition of the boundary of Ω into Γ^D and Γ^N and have the same vertices on the interface Γ^I for both fluid and solid (i.e. they are conformal meshes).

We define the following polynomial spaces:

$$\begin{aligned} P_1(K) &= \{q|_K \text{ with } q : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \text{ polynomial of degree } \leq 1\}, \\ P_b(K) &= \{q + \alpha \lambda_b^K : q \in P_1(K), \alpha \in \mathbb{R}\}, \end{aligned}$$

where λ_b^K is the bubble function of element K . We consider the following spaces of finite elements:

$$X_h = \left\{ \mathbf{w}_h \in (C^0(\overline{\Omega}))^d : \mathbf{w}_{h|_K} \in (P_b(K))^d \ \forall K \in \mathfrak{T}_h^f, \mathbf{w}_{h|_K} \in (P_1(K))^d \ \forall K \in \mathfrak{T}_h^s \right\}, \quad (5.1)$$

$$X_{0h} = \left\{ \mathbf{w}_h \in X_h : \mathbf{w}_h = \mathbf{0} \text{ on } \Gamma^D \right\}, \quad (5.2)$$

$$V_h = \left\{ \varphi_h \in C^0(\overline{\Omega}^f) : \varphi_{h|_K} \in P_1(K) \ \forall K \in \mathfrak{T}_h^f \right\}. \quad (5.3)$$

Let us notice that for the continuity through the fluid-solid interface it is enough that the displacement components coincide at the vertices on this interface because bubbles are null on the boundaries of the mesh elements. In order to obtain a fully discrete scheme of the time semi-discretized problem (4.4)-(4.5) we use spaces X_h , X_{0h} and V_h to approximate function spaces $\mathbf{H}^1(\Omega)$, $\mathbf{H}_{\Gamma^D}^1(\Omega)$ and $L^2(\Omega^f)$, respectively. Thus, we obtain the following fully discrete problem:

(LG) Pure Lagrange-Galerkin problem. Find two sequences of functions $\widehat{\mathbf{u}}_{\Delta t, h} = \{\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{n+3/2}\}_{n=0}^{N-1} \in [X_h]^N$ and $\widehat{\pi}_{m, \Delta t, h} = \{\pi_{m, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}\}_{n=0}^{N-1} \in [V_h]^N$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\Omega} \rho^{n+1/2} \circ X_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2} \det F_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2} \frac{\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{n+3/2} - 2\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2} + \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{n-1/2}}{\Delta t^2} \cdot \mathbf{z}_h \, dp \\ & \quad - \int_{\Omega^f} \pi_{m, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2} \det F_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2} (F_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2})^{-t} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{z}_h \, dp \\ & + \eta \int_{\Omega^f} \det F_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2} \frac{\nabla \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{n+3/2} - \nabla \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{n-1/2}}{2\Delta t} (F_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2})^{-1} (F_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2})^{-t} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{z}_h \, dp \\ & + \eta \int_{\Omega^f} \det F_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2} (F_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2})^{-t} \frac{(\nabla \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{n+3/2})^t - (\nabla \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{n-1/2})^t}{2\Delta t} (F_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2})^{-t} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{z}_h \, dp \\ & \quad + \frac{\lambda}{2} \int_{\Omega^s} \left(\text{Div } \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{n+3/2} + \text{Div } \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{n-1/2} \right) \text{Div } \mathbf{z}_h \, dp \\ & + \mu \int_{\Omega^s} \left(\mathcal{E}(\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{n+3/2}) + \mathcal{E}(\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{n-1/2}) \right) \cdot \mathcal{E}(\mathbf{z}_h) \, dp = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{b}^{n+1/2} \circ X_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2} \cdot \mathbf{z}_h \det F_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2} \, dp \\ & + \int_{\Gamma^N} |(F_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2})^{-t} \mathbf{m}| \det F_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2} \mathbf{h}^{n+1/2} \circ X_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2} \cdot \mathbf{z}_h \, dA_p \ \forall \mathbf{z}_h \in X_{0h}, \quad (5.4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\int_{\Omega^f} \det F_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2} \frac{\nabla \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{n+3/2} - \nabla \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{n-1/2}}{2\Delta t} \cdot (F_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2})^{-t} q_h \, dp = 0 \ \forall q_h \in V_h, \quad (5.5)$$

for $0 \leq n \leq N - 1$, subject to the initial and boundary conditions

$$\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{-1/2}(p) = \mathbf{u}^{-1/2}(p) \text{ for all node } p \text{ of mesh } \mathfrak{T}_h^f \cup \mathfrak{T}_h^s, \quad (5.6)$$

$$\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{1/2}(p) = \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{-1/2}(p) + \mathbf{v}^0(p)\Delta t \text{ for all node } p \text{ of mesh } \mathfrak{T}_h^f \cup \mathfrak{T}_h^s, \quad (5.7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{n+3/2}(p) &= \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{n-1/2}(p) + 2\Delta t \mathbf{v}_D^{n+1/2} \left(X_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}(p) \right) \\ &\text{for all node } p \text{ of mesh } \mathfrak{T}_h^f \cup \mathfrak{T}_h^s \text{ on } \Gamma^D, \text{ and } 0 \leq n \leq N - 1, \end{aligned} \quad (5.8)$$

and where

$$X_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}(p) := p + \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}(p), \quad (5.9)$$

$$F_{\Delta t, h|K}^{n+1/2} := I + \nabla \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h|K}^{n+1/2}, \quad (5.10)$$

for $p \in \overline{\Omega}$, $K \in \mathfrak{T}_h^f \cup \mathfrak{T}_h^s$ and $0 \leq n \leq N - 1$. Notice that for displacement methods as the one above, the fluid-solid coupling at the interface is straightforward. In particular, the interface kinematic condition is included in the definition of the functional space where the solution is looked for.

By using the solution of problem **(LG)**, we can obtain approximations of the followings fields: the material description of the velocity at times $\{t_{n+1}\}_{n=0}^{N-1}$, the motion at times $\{t_{n+1}\}_{n=0}^{N-1}$, the spatial description of the velocity at times $\{t_{n+1}\}_{n=0}^{N-1}$, the pressure in spatial coordinates at times $\{t_{n+1/2}\}_{n=0}^{N-1}$ and the stress tensor in spatial coordinates at times $\{t_{n+1/2}\}_{n=0}^{N-1}$. These approximations will be denoted respectively by $\{\mathbf{v}_{m, \Delta t, h}^{n+1}\}_{n=0}^{N-1}$, $\{X_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1}\}_{n=0}^{N-1}$, $\{\mathbf{v}_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1}\}_{n=0}^{N-1}$, $\{\pi_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}\}_{n=0}^{N-1}$ and $\{T_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}\}_{n=0}^{N-1}$. Moreover, we will denote by $\{p_i^h\}_{i=1}^{N_v^h}$, $\{p_i^{f, h}\}_{i=1}^{N_v^{f, h}}$ and $\{p_i^{s, h}\}_{i=1}^{N_v^{s, h}}$ the vertices of meshes $\mathfrak{T}_h^f \cup \mathfrak{T}_h^s$, $\mathfrak{T}_h^f$ and $\mathfrak{T}_h^s$, respectively. Notice that $\mathfrak{T}_h^f$ and $\mathfrak{T}_h^s$ have the same vertices on the interface, then $N_v^h = N_v^{f, h} + N_v^{s, h} - N_v^{I, h}$, being $N_v^{I, h}$ the number of vertices on the interface Γ^I . Analogously, let us denote by $\tilde{\mathfrak{T}}_h^{f, l}$ and $\tilde{\mathfrak{T}}_h^{s, l}$ the moved meshes at time t_l , being $\{X_{\Delta t, h}^l(p_i^{f, h})\}_{i=1}^{N_v^{f, h}}$ and $\{X_{\Delta t, h}^l(p_i^{s, h})\}_{i=1}^{N_v^{s, h}}$ the vertices of these meshes, respectively.

- **Approximation of the material description of the velocity.** It can be easily obtained by using Taylor expansions (4.6) and (4.7). More precisely, since

$$\mathbf{v}_m^{n+1}(p) = \frac{\mathbf{u}^{n+3/2}(p) - \mathbf{u}^{n+1/2}(p)}{\Delta t} + O(\Delta t^2),$$

we define

$$\mathbf{v}_{m, \Delta t, h}^{n+1}(p) := \frac{\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{n+3/2}(p) - \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}(p)}{\Delta t},$$

for $p \in \overline{\Omega}$ and $0 \leq n \leq N - 1$.

- **Motion approximation at times $\{t_{n+1}\}_{n=0}^{N-1}$.** Noting that $\mathbf{u}(p, t) = X(p, t) - p$ and using (4.6) and (4.7), we obtain

$$X^{n+1}(p) = p + \frac{\mathbf{u}^{n+3/2}(p) + \mathbf{u}^{n+1/2}(p)}{2} + O(\Delta t^2).$$

Then we define the approximation

$$X_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1}(p) := p + \frac{\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{n+3/2}(p) + \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}(p)}{2},$$

for $p \in \overline{\Omega}$ and $0 \leq n \leq N - 1$.

- **Approximation of the spatial description of the velocity.** In order to obtain an approximate velocity in Eulerian coordinates, it will be considered as a piecewise linear function on the moved mesh $\tilde{\mathfrak{T}}_h^{f, n+1} \cup \tilde{\mathfrak{T}}_h^{s, n+1}$, being $\{X_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1}(p_i^h)\}_{i=1}^{N_v^h}$ the vertices of this mesh. The values of $\mathbf{v}_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1}$ at vertices $\{X_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1}(p_i^h)\}_{i=1}^{N_v^h}$ can be obtained by using $\mathbf{v}_{m, \Delta t, h}^{n+1}$. Since we have

$$\mathbf{v}^{n+1}(X_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1}(p_i^h)) \simeq \mathbf{v}^{n+1}(X^{n+1}(p_i^h)) = \mathbf{v}_m^{n+1}(p_i^h) \simeq \mathbf{v}_{m, \Delta t, h}^{n+1}(p_i^h),$$

we take the approximation

$$\mathbf{v}_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1}(X_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1}(p_i^h)) := \mathbf{v}_{m, \Delta t, h}^{n+1}(p_i^h), \quad (5.11)$$

for $0 \leq n \leq N-1$. Notice that $\bigcup_{K \in \tilde{\mathfrak{T}}_h^{f, n+1} \cup \tilde{\mathfrak{T}}_h^{s, n+1}} K \sim \bar{\Omega}_{t_{n+1}}$.

- **Approximate pressure in spatial coordinates.** In order to approximate this field we use analogous procedures to the ones in the previous item. That is, we consider the approximate pressure in spatial coordinates as a piecewise linear function on the moved mesh $\tilde{\mathfrak{T}}_h^{f, n+1/2}$. The values of the approximate pressure at vertices $\{X_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}(p_i^{f, h})\}_{i=1}^{N_v^{f, h}}$ are obtained as follows: firstly, we notice that

$$\pi^{n+1/2}(X_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}(p_i^{f, h})) \simeq \pi^{n+1/2}(X^{n+1/2}(p_i^{f, h})) = \pi_m^{n+1/2}(p_i^{f, h}) \simeq \pi_{m, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}(p_i^{f, h}),$$

and then we take

$$\pi_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}(X_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}(p_i^{f, h})) := \pi_{m, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}(p_i^{f, h}),$$

for $0 \leq n \leq N-1$. Notice that $\bigcup_{K \in \tilde{\mathfrak{T}}_h^{f, n+1/2}} K \sim \bar{\Omega}_{t_{n+1/2}}^f$.

- **Approximation of the spatial stress tensor in the solid.** In order to obtain the Cauchy stress tensor in spatial coordinates we use analogous procedures to the ones above. That is, we consider the approximate stress tensor in spatial coordinates as a piecewise linear function on the moved mesh $\tilde{\mathfrak{T}}_h^{s, n+1/2}$, being $\{X_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}(p_i^{s, h})\}_{i=1}^{N_v^{s, h}}$ the vertices of this mesh. The values of the approximate stress tensor at vertices $\{X_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}(p_i^{s, h})\}_{i=1}^{N_v^{s, h}}$ are obtained as follows. Firstly, for a given element K^s of the mesh $\mathfrak{T}_h^s$ and a vertex $p_i^{s, h} \in K^s$, from (3.13) we have

$$\begin{aligned} T^{n+1/2}(X_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}(p_i^{s, h})) &\simeq T^{n+1/2}(X^{n+1/2}(p_i^{s, h})) = T_m^{n+1/2}(p_i^{s, h}) \\ &= \frac{1}{\det F^{n+1/2}(p_i^{s, h})} \left(\lambda \operatorname{Div} \mathbf{u}(p_i^{s, h}, t_{n+1/2}) I + 2\mu \mathcal{E}(\mathbf{u})(p_i^{s, h}, t_{n+1/2}) \right) (F^{n+1/2})^t(p_i^{s, h}) \\ &\simeq \frac{1}{\det F_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}|_{K^s}} \left(\lambda (\operatorname{Div} \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2})|_{K^s} I + 2\mu \mathcal{E}(\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2})|_{K^s} \right) (F_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}|_{K^s})^t. \end{aligned}$$

Then, we define the approximation

$$\begin{aligned} T_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}(X_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}(p_i^{s, h})) &:= \frac{1}{n_i} \sum_{K^s \in E_i^s} \frac{1}{\det F_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}|_{K^s}} \left(\lambda (\operatorname{Div} \mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2})|_{K^s} I \right. \\ &\quad \left. + 2\mu \mathcal{E}(\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2})|_{K^s} \right) (F_{\Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}|_{K^s})^t, \end{aligned} \quad (5.12)$$

for $0 \leq n \leq N-1$, where E_i^s is the set of elements of $\mathfrak{T}_h^s$ that share vertex $p_i^{s, h}$ and n_i is the number of elements of E_i^s . Notice that $\bigcup_{K \in \tilde{\mathfrak{T}}_h^{s, n+1/2}} K \sim \bar{\Omega}_{t_{n+1/2}}^s$.

6. Reinitialization of the pure Lagrange-Galerkin scheme. Notice that for pure-Lagrangian schemes, the computational domain is the same for all time steps. However, in order to calculate the velocity, the pressure or the stress tensor in Eulerian coordinates the moved mesh is used. For real fluid-structure problems, this mesh may have large deformations. When this happens it is necessary to remesh and reinitialize the motion.

In this section we propose a method to do this for the pure Lagrange-Galerkin scheme (5.4)-(5.10). Let us assume that we have decided to reinitialize this problem at time $t_{r-1/2}$ being $1 \leq r \leq N-1$. Then, we first compute $\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{r+1/2}$ by using (5.4), (5.5) and (5.8) for $n = r-1$. The objective of this section is the numerical solution of problem (2.9)-(2.12), (3.11)-(3.13) at times $t > t_{r+1/2}$. For this purpose, we first obtain a new formulation of the problem written in the reference domain $\bar{\Omega}_{t_{r-1/2}}$. It can be obtained by using analogous procedures to the ones in Section 3 but using the change of variable $x = X_{t_{r-1/2}}(y, t)$.

Remark 6.1. Notice that in this paper we consider a fluid-structure interaction problem in which the solid presents small deformations, that is, the displacement gradient $\nabla \mathbf{u}$ in the solid is small. We want to emphasize that the derivation of the linearized constitutive equation (3.13) is based on this assumption. More precisely, this constitutive equation is obtained neglecting the terms of order $o(\nabla \mathbf{u})$ and assuming the residual stress in the reference configuration ($t = t_0$) vanishes (see [16] for details). Similarly, we deduce the following linear constitutive equation in configuration $\Omega_{t_{r-1/2}}^s$

$$\begin{aligned} T_{t_{r-1/2}}(y, t) \det F_{t_{r-1/2}}(y, t) F_{t_{r-1/2}}^{-t}(y, t) &= \lambda \operatorname{div}_y \mathbf{u}_{t_{r-1/2}}(y, t) I \\ + \mu (\operatorname{grad}_y \mathbf{u}_{t_{r-1/2}}(y, t) + (\operatorname{grad}_y \mathbf{u}_{t_{r-1/2}})^t(y, t)) &+ T(y, t_{r-1/2}), \end{aligned} \quad (6.1)$$

for $(y, t) \in \Omega_{t_{r-1/2}}^s \times (t_0, T)$. We notice that $T(y, t_{r-1/2})$ is the residual stress at time $t_{r-1/2}$.

An analogous scheme to the one introduced in Section 4 is considered for time discretization of this new strong problem. For space discretization, we use continuous piecewise-linear+bubble finite element for each fluid displacement component and continuous piecewise-linear for pressure and each solid displacement component.

Let us suppose $\Omega_{t_{r-1/2}}^f$ and $\Omega_{t_{r-1/2}}^s$ are two bounded domains in $\mathbb{R}^d$ with Lipschitz polygonal boundaries. Let us consider two suitable families of regular triangulations of $\overline{\Omega}_{t_{r-1/2}}^f$ and $\overline{\Omega}_{t_{r-1/2}}^s$ to be denoted by $\mathfrak{T}_h^{f, r-1/2}$ and $\mathfrak{T}_h^{s, r-1/2}$ respectively, both consisting of elements K of diameter $\leq h$. Moreover, let us assume they have the same vertices on the interface and that they are compatible with the partition of the boundary of $\Omega_{t_{r-1/2}}$ into $\Gamma_{t_{r-1/2}}^D$ and $\Gamma_{t_{r-1/2}}^N$. We consider the following finite element spaces:

$$\begin{aligned} X_h^{r-1/2} &= \left\{ \mathbf{w}_h \in (C^0(\overline{\Omega}_{t_{r-1/2}}^f))^d : \mathbf{w}_{h|_K} \in (P_b(K))^d \quad \forall K \in \mathfrak{T}_h^{f, r-1/2}, \right. \\ &\quad \left. \mathbf{w}_{h|_K} \in (P_1(K))^d \quad \forall K \in \mathfrak{T}_h^{s, r-1/2} \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (6.2)$$

$$X_{0h}^{r-1/2} = \left\{ \mathbf{w}_h \in X_h^{r-1/2} : \mathbf{w}_h = \mathbf{0} \text{ on } \Gamma_{t_{r-1/2}}^D \right\}, \quad (6.3)$$

$$V_h^{r-1/2} = \left\{ \varphi_h \in C^0(\overline{\Omega}_{t_{r-1/2}}^f) : \varphi_{h|_K} \in P_1(K) \quad \forall K \in \mathfrak{T}_h^{f, r-1/2} \right\}. \quad (6.4)$$

In what follows we will denote by $\Psi_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^l$ approximations of $\Psi_{t_{r-1/2}}^l$ obtained with a fully discretized scheme, being $\Psi = \mathbf{u}, X, F, \pi$. Now we are in a position to introduce the approximate problem:

Pure Lagrange-Galerkin scheme in $\overline{\Omega}_{t_{r-1/2}} \times (t_{r-1/2}, T)$. Find two sequences of functions $\widehat{\mathbf{u}}_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h} =$

$\{\mathbf{u}_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+3/2}\}_{n=r}^{N-1} \in [X_h^{r-1/2}]^{N-r}$ and $\widehat{\pi}_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h} = \{\pi_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}\}_{n=r}^{N-1} \in [V_h^{r-1/2}]^{N-r}$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{\Omega_{t_{r-1/2}}} \rho^{n+1/2} \circ X_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2} \det F_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2} \frac{\mathbf{u}_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+3/2} - 2\mathbf{u}_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2} + \mathbf{u}_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n-1/2}}{\Delta t^2} \cdot \mathbf{z}_h \, dy \\ &\quad - \int_{\Omega_{t_{r-1/2}}^f} \pi_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2} \det F_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2} (F_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2})^{-t} \cdot \operatorname{grad} \mathbf{z}_h \, dy \\ &\quad + \eta \int_{\Omega_{t_{r-1/2}}^f} \det F_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2} \frac{\operatorname{grad} \mathbf{u}_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+3/2} - \operatorname{grad} \mathbf{u}_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n-1/2}}{2\Delta t} \\ &\quad (F_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2})^{-1} (F_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2})^{-t} \cdot \operatorname{grad} \mathbf{z}_h \, dy + \eta \int_{\Omega_{t_{r-1/2}}^f} \det F_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2} (F_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2})^{-t} \\ &\quad \frac{(\operatorname{grad} \mathbf{u}_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+3/2})^t - (\operatorname{grad} \mathbf{u}_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n-1/2})^t}{2\Delta t} (F_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2})^{-t} \cdot \operatorname{grad} \mathbf{z}_h \, dy \\ &\quad + \frac{\lambda}{2} \int_{\Omega_{t_{r-1/2}}^s} \left(\operatorname{div} \mathbf{u}_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+3/2} + \operatorname{div} \mathbf{u}_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n-1/2} \right) \operatorname{div} \mathbf{z}_h \, dy \\ &\quad + \mu \int_{\Omega_{t_{r-1/2}}^s} \left(\mathcal{E}(\mathbf{u}_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+3/2}) + \mathcal{E}(\mathbf{u}_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n-1/2}) \right) \cdot \mathcal{E}(\mathbf{z}_h) \, dy \\ &= \int_{\Omega_{t_{r-1/2}}} \mathbf{b}^{n+1/2} \circ X_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2} \cdot \mathbf{z}_h \det F_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2} \, dy - \int_{\Omega_{t_{r-1/2}}^s} T_{\Delta t, h}^{r-1/2}(y) \cdot \operatorname{grad} \mathbf{z}_h \, dy \end{aligned}$$

$$+ \int_{\Gamma_{t_{r-1/2}}^N} |(F_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2})^{-t} \mathbf{m}_{t_{r-1/2}}| \det F_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2} \mathbf{h}^{n+1/2} \circ X_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2} \cdot \mathbf{z}_h dA_y, \quad (6.5)$$

$$\int_{\Omega_{t_{r-1/2}}^f} \det F_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2} \frac{\text{grad } \mathbf{u}_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+3/2} - \text{grad } \mathbf{u}_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n-1/2}}{2\Delta t} \cdot (F_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2})^{-t} q_h dy = 0, \quad (6.6)$$

$\forall \mathbf{z}_h \in X_{0h}^{r-1/2}$, $\forall q_h \in V_h^{r-1/2}$, $r \leq n \leq N-1$, and where

$$\begin{aligned} X_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}(y) &:= y + \mathbf{u}_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}(y), \\ F_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h|K}^{n+1/2} &:= I + \text{grad } \mathbf{u}_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h|K}^{n+1/2}, \end{aligned}$$

for $y \in \overline{\Omega}_{t_{r-1/2}}$, $K \in \mathfrak{T}_h^{f, r-1/2} \cup \mathfrak{T}_h^{s, r-1/2}$ and $r \leq n \leq N-1$. In the above equation, $\mathbf{m}_{t_{r-1/2}}$ is the outward unit normal vector to $\partial\Omega_{t_{r-1/2}}$ and $\mathcal{E}(\Psi)(y, t) = 1/2(\text{grad } \Psi(y, t) + (\text{grad } \Psi)^t(y, t))$ for a function $\Psi(y, t)$. Notice that the residual stress at time $t_{r-1/2}$ is unknown. It is approximated by using (5.12).

Remark 6.2. By using analogous procedures to the ones in Remarks 4.1 and 4.2, we can obtain approximate initial and Dirichlet boundary conditions for displacement $\mathbf{u}_{t_{r-1/2}}$. More precisely, in order to obtain the initial conditions for scheme (6.5)-(6.6), we observe that $\mathbf{u}_{r-1/2}^{r-1/2}(y) = \mathbf{0} \ \forall y \in \overline{\Omega}_{t_{r-1/2}}$. Moreover, by using Taylor expansions and that $\mathbf{u}_{r-1/2}^{r-1/2} \equiv \mathbf{0}$, we deduce

$$\mathbf{u}_{r-1/2}^{r+1/2}(y) = \Delta t \mathbf{v}^r \left(y + \mathbf{v}^r(y) \frac{1}{2} \Delta t \right) + O(\Delta t^3).$$

Then we take

$$\mathbf{u}_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{r-1/2}(y) = \mathbf{0}, \quad \mathbf{u}_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{r+1/2}(y) = \Delta t \mathbf{v}_{\Delta t, h}^r \left(y + \mathbf{v}_{\Delta t, h}^r(y) \frac{1}{2} \Delta t \right), \quad (6.7)$$

$\forall y \in \overline{\Omega}_{t_{r-1/2}}$. Notice that, in order to obtain the above approximate initial condition for $\mathbf{u}_{t_{r-1/2}}(y, t_{r+1/2})$ we need $\mathbf{v}_{\Delta t, h}^r$ that is calculated by using (5.11). Similarly, we can obtain approximate Dirichlet boundary conditions for displacement $\mathbf{u}_{t_{r-1/2}}$. More precisely, by using that

$$\mathbf{u}_{r-1/2}^{n+3/2}(y) = \mathbf{u}_{r-1/2}^{n-1/2}(y) + 2\Delta t \mathbf{v}^{n+1/2} \left(X_{r-1/2}^{n+1/2}(y) \right) + O(\Delta t^3),$$

we deduce the following Dirichlet boundary condition for $\mathbf{u}_{r-1/2}^{n+3/2}$:

$$\mathbf{u}_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+3/2}(y) = \mathbf{u}_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n-1/2}(y) + 2\Delta t \mathbf{v}_D^{n+1/2} \left(X_{r-1/2, \Delta t, h}^{n+1/2}(y) \right), \quad (6.8)$$

for $y \in \Gamma_{t_{r-1/2}}^D$ and $r \leq n \leq N-1$.

Remark 6.3. By using analogous procedures to the ones in Section 5, we can obtain, by using the solution of problem (6.5)-(6.8), approximations of the pressure in spatial coordinates, the stress tensor in spatial coordinates, the velocity and the motion at time instants $t > t_{r-1/2}$.

7. Numerical results. In order to assess the performance of the numerical method introduced in this article, we solve three test problems in two space dimensions. The first one is an academic problem which is used to check the convergence rates. The second one is the motion of an elastic circular disk in a cavity filled with an incompressible Newtonian viscous fluid. Different values for disk density and fluid viscosity are considered. This problem has been solved with the method described in the present paper, being necessary to remesh and to reinitialize the motion from time to time. Finally, the third example is a free surface problem. More precisely, we consider an example of sloshing of an incompressible Newtonian viscous fluid where a circular disk is submerged.

In Example 1, we calculate the error between discrete solutions $\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}$, $\mathbf{v}_{\Delta t, h}$, $\pi_{\Delta t, h}$, and exact solutions $\mathbf{u}$, $\mathbf{v}$, π . For this, we approximate the theoretical $H^1(\Omega_\tau)$ and $L^2(\Omega_\tau)$ norms by using a quadrature formula exact for polynomials of degree 5. Moreover, domain at time τ with $\tau > t_0$, is calculated by using the approximate motion. The function spaces endowed with these norms are denoted by $H_h^1(\Omega_\tau)$ and $L_h^2(\Omega_\tau)$, respectively. Furthermore, we introduce the notation $\mathbf{H}_h^1(\Omega_\tau) = (H_h^1(\Omega_\tau))^2$, $\mathbf{L}_h^2(\Omega_\tau) = (L_h^2(\Omega_\tau))^2$ and denote by $l^\infty(\mathcal{A}^n)$, being

$$\mathcal{A}^n = \mathbf{L}_h^2(\Omega), \mathbf{H}_h^1(\Omega), \mathbf{L}_h^2(\Omega_{t_{n+1}}), \mathbf{H}_h^1(\Omega_{t_{n+1}}), L_h^2(\Omega_{t_{n+1/2}}), H_h^1(\Omega_{t_{n+1/2}}),$$

the space of sequences in $\{\mathcal{A}^n\}_n$ equipped with the norm $\left\| \widehat{\Psi} \right\|_{l^\infty(\mathcal{A}^n)} := \max_n \|\Psi^n\|_{\mathcal{A}^n}$.

Moreover, all integrals appearing in the discrete weak formulations introduced above are approximated by using an exact quadrature formula for polynomials of degree 5.

Example 1

This is a problem aiming to analyze the rates of convergence of the pure-Lagrangian scheme proposed in this paper. The fluid domain is $\Omega^f = (0, 1) \times (0, 1)$ and the solid domain is $\Omega^s = (1, 2) \times (0, 1)$, the

FIG. 7.1. Example 1: computed $l^\infty(L_h^2)$ errors, in log-log scale, versus the number of time steps for a fixed spatial mesh of 251×251 vertices.

FIG. 7.2. Example 1: computed $l^\infty(L_h^2)$ (left) and $l^\infty(H_h^1)$ (right) errors, in log-log scale, versus $1/h$ for $\Delta t = 1/2500$.

initial time is $t_0 = 0$ and the final time is $T = 1$. The physical parameters are $\rho = 1$, $\lambda = 1$, $\mu = 1$ and $\eta = 0.1$. We adjust the body force and the boundary conditions so that the solution of the problem is the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{v}(x_1, x_2, t) &= (0.01\exp(t), 0.01\exp(t)\cos(x_1 - 0.01\exp(t) - 1)), \\ \pi(x_1, x_2, t) &= \exp(t)\sin(x_1 - 0.01\exp(t) - 1), \\ \mathbf{u}(p_1, p_2, t) &= (0.01\exp(t), 0.01\exp(t)\cos(p_1 - 1)). \end{aligned}$$

Notice that for this example, equations (3.19) and (3.24) are satisfied. We solve this problem by using the pure Lagrange-Galerkin method introduced in this paper (**LG**). The initial conditions $\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{-1/2}$ and $\mathbf{u}_{\Delta t, h}^{1/2}$ are calculated by (5.6) and (5.7), respectively. In Figure 7.1, we have fixed a uniform spatial mesh of 251×251 vertices and show the $l^\infty(\mathbf{L}_h^2(\Omega))$ displacement error, the $l^\infty(\mathbf{L}_h^2(\Omega_{t_{n+1}}))$ velocity error and the $l^\infty(L_h^2(\Omega_{t_{n+1/2}}))$ pressure error versus the number of time steps. These results show that scheme (**LG**) possesses second-order accuracy in time for displacement and velocity and first-order accuracy in time for pressure. Notice that, for fixed h , we can observe an increasing error as the time step decreases below a threshold. This seems to be due to that terms with Δt in the denominator would be present in the error expression. In Figure 7.2 we represent the computed $l^\infty(L_h^2)$ and $l^\infty(H_h^1)$ errors for displacement,

velocity and pressure versus $1/h$, for a fixed small time step, namely $\Delta t = 0.0004$. We can observe that the **(LG)** scheme possesses second-order accuracy in space in the $l^\infty(L_h^2)$ -norm and first-order accuracy in space in the $l^\infty(H_h^1)$ -norm.

Example 2

In this example we consider the motion of an elastic circular disk in a rectangular cavity filled with an incompressible Newtonian viscous fluid. The only force considered is gravity. The computational domain is $\Omega = (0, 2) \times (0, 6)$, the diameter of the disk is $d = 0.25$ and the fluid density is $\rho^f = 1$. The values of Young modulus and Poisson ratio for the disk are 10^8 and 0.3 , respectively. For these values, the solid is visually non-deformable. We solve this problem for different viscosity coefficients ($\eta = 0.1$, $\eta = 0.01$) and for different disk densities ($\rho^s = 0.5$, $\rho^s = 1.25$, $\rho^s = 1.5$), with the pure-Lagrangian method **(LG)**, but remeshing and reinitializing the motion at certain times. Specifically, for $\eta = 0.1$ (respectively, for $\eta = 0.01$) the problem is reinitialized every second being $\Delta t = 0.02$ (respectively, every 0.01 seconds being $\Delta t = 0.001$). The fluid and the disk are initially at rest. Moreover, when $\rho^s > \rho^f$ the fluid velocity is $\mathbf{0}$ on the boundary of Ω , that is $\mathbf{v}_D \equiv \mathbf{0}$. However, when $\rho^s < \rho^f$, we impose null Neumann condition (force-free) at the upper horizontal boundary, while at the vertical boundaries and at the lower horizontal boundary the velocity is zero (no-slip boundary condition). The considered Lagrangian meshes are finer close to the disk. More precisely, for all meshes the minimum mesh-size is $h_{min} = 0.001$ and the maximum one is $h_{max} = 0.07$. In Figures 7.3 and 7.4 we show the x-coordinate and y-coordinate

FIG. 7.3. Motion of a disk: histories of the x-coordinate (left) and y-coordinate (right) of the disk center for $\eta = 0.1$ and $\rho^s = 1.25$, and for $\Delta t = 0.02$.

FIG. 7.4. Motion of a disk: histories of the x-coordinate (left) and y-coordinate (right) of the disk center for $\eta = 0.01$ and $\rho^s = 1.5$, and for $\Delta t = 0.001$.

of the center of the disk along the time for $\mu = 0.1$, $\rho^s = 1.25$ and for $\mu = 0.01$, $\rho^s = 1.5$, respectively. As expected, we can observe that the disk falls much faster when its density is increased and viscosity of the fluid is reduced. In Figures 7.5 and 7.6 we represent the streamlines and the isopressure contours at two times for $\mu = 0.1$ and $\rho^s = 1.25$. Similarly, in Figures 7.7 and 7.8 the streamlines and the isopressure contours at two times and for $\mu = 0.01$ and $\rho^s = 1.5$ are shown. Notice that, for both experiments, a perfect symmetric solution is obtained at each time. In [15] numerical results for similar experiments are presented. Moreover, we show the numerical results obtained for $\mu = 0.1$ and $\rho^s = 0.5$.

FIG. 7.5. Motion of a disk: numerical streamlines for $\eta = 0.1$ and $\rho^s = 1.25$ at $t = 14.3$ and $t = 42$, respectively, and for $\Delta t = 0.02$.

FIG. 7.6. Motion of a disk: isopressure contours for $\eta = 0.1$ and $\rho^s = 1.25$ at $t = 14.295$ and $t = 41.99$, respectively, and for $\Delta t = 0.02$.

More precisely, in Figures 7.9, 7.10 and 7.11 we show the x-coordinate and y-coordinate of the center

FIG. 7.7. Motion of a disk: numerical streamlines for $\eta = 0.01$ and $\rho^s = 1.5$ at $t = 2.25$ and $t = 5.49$, respectively, and for $\Delta t = 0.001$.

FIG. 7.8. Motion of a disk: isopressure contours for $\eta = 0.01$ and $\rho^s = 1.5$ at $t = 2.2495$ and $t = 5.4895$, respectively, and for $\Delta t = 0.001$.

of the disk along the time and the streamlines and the isopressure contours at two times, respectively. Finally, in order to show the behaviour of the pure-Lagrangian scheme for large solid deformation, we

FIG. 7.9. Motion of a disk: histories of the x -coordinate (left) and y -coordinate (right) of the disk center for $\eta = 0.1$ and $\rho^s = 0.5$, and for $\Delta t = 0.02$.

FIG. 7.10. Motion of a disk: numerical streamlines for $\eta = 0.1$ and $\rho^s = 0.5$ at $t = 4$ and $t = 12$, respectively, and for $\Delta t = 0.02$.

solve the problem described above for $\eta = 0.1$, $\rho^s = 1.25$, $E = 2$ and $\nu = 0.3$, with the pure-Lagrangian method (**LG**). The obtained results are depicted in Figures 7.12 and 7.13 where the streamlines at $t = 1$ and the isopressure contours at $t = 0.99$ are shown, respectively. In this case reinitialization was not done.

Example 3

FIG. 7.11. *Motion of a disk: isopressure contours for $\eta = 0.1$ and $\rho^s = 0.5$ at $t = 3.99$ and $t = 11.99$, respectively, and for $\Delta t = 0.02$.*

FIG. 7.12. *Motion of a disk: numerical streamlines for $\eta = 0.1$, $\rho^s = 1.25$, $E = 2$ and $\nu = 0.3$ at $t = 1$, for $\Delta t = 0.02$.*

FIG. 7.13. *Motion of a disk: isopressure contours for $\eta = 0.1$, $\rho^s = 1.25$, $E = 2$ and $\nu = 0.3$ at $t = 0.99$, for $\Delta t = 0.02$.*

In this example we simulate the large amplitude sloshing of a fluid with a submerged disk. There are

FIG. 7.14. *Sloshing waves: histories of the center of the disk (left) and of wave height at the walls (right), for a spatial mesh of 11097 vertices and $\Delta t = 0.02$.*

FIG. 7.15. *Sloshing waves: instantaneous domain configuration, streamlines and isopressure contours at $t = 14$, and for a spatial mesh of 11097 vertices and $\Delta t = 0.02$.*

several papers in the literature solving this problem but without the submerged body (see, for instance, [17], [20] and [2]). The width of the tank is 0.8 m , the depth is 0.3 m and the diameter of the circle is $d = 0.12\text{ m}$. The values of Young modulus and Poisson ratio for the solid are 10^8 and 0.3 , respectively. The liquid in the tank is subject to a sinusoidal horizontal force. More precisely, the body force is

$$\mathbf{b}(x, t) = \rho(x, t)(A g \sin(\omega t), -g),$$

where A is an arbitrary constant governing the amplitude of the excitation, g is the gravity acceleration and ω is the excitation frequency. We have taken, $A = 0.01$, $\rho = 1000\text{ kg/m}^3$, $g = 9.8\text{ m/s}^2$ and $\omega = 5.642\text{ rad/s}$. Using these parameters, experimental results show that the first resonance frequency of the tank filled with inviscid fluid and using the potential theory is 0.898 Hz . Moreover, the viscosity

coefficient has been taken $\eta = 1Pa.s$. The only body force acting on the solid is gravity. At the vertical boundaries the horizontal velocity is zero, at the lower horizontal boundary the vertical velocity is zero and at the upper horizontal boundary we impose null Neumann condition (force-free). In order to show the behaviour of the pure-Lagrangian scheme for large mesh distortion, we solve this problem with the pure-Lagrangian method (**LG**) without reinitializing. Notice that in pure-Lagrangian methods the computational domain is the reference domain; in this case it is $\Omega = (0, 0.8) \times (0, 0.3)$. Figure (7.14) shows the trajectory of the center of the disk (left) and the vertical displacement of the upper corner nodes at the wall tank, as a function of time (right). In Figure 7.15 we represent an instantaneous configuration of the domain, the streamlines and the isopressure contours.

8. Conclusions. We have introduced a pure Lagrange-Galerkin scheme for solving fluid-structure interaction problems. This scheme is written in Lagrangian coordinates and in terms of displacement rather than velocity and therefore it is useful for solving free surface problems and fluid-structure interaction problems. For moderate to high-Reynolds number flows, this scheme can lead to high distortion in the mesh elements. When this happens it is necessary to remesh and reinitialize the scheme at certain time. We have proposed a method for reinitialization. Numerical tests have been presented to assess the effectiveness of the method and to analyze its rates of convergence. In particular, we have considered the motion of an elastic circular disk in a rectangular cavity filled with an incompressible Newtonian viscous fluid. This problem has been solved with the pure-Lagrangian method but remeshing and reinitializing at certain times are needed. Moreover, we have considered a sloshing problem of a fluid containing an elastic disk that has been solved without any reinitialization.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. N. ARNOLD AND M. FORTIN, *A stable finite element for the Stokes equations*, *Calcolo*, 21 (1984), pp. 337–344.
- [2] M. BENÍTEZ AND A. BERMÚDEZ, *Pure lagrangian and semi-lagrangian finite element methods for the numerical solution of Navier-Stokes equations*, *Appl. Numer. Math.*, to appear.
- [3] ———, *A second order characteristics finite element scheme for natural convection problems*, *J. Comput. Appl. Math.*, 235 (2011), pp. 3270–3284.
- [4] ———, *Numerical Analysis of a second-order pure Lagrange-Galerkin method for convection-diffusion problems. Part I: time discretization*, *SIAM. J. Numer. Anal.*, 50 (2012), pp. 858–882.
- [5] ———, *Numerical Analysis of a second-order pure Lagrange-Galerkin method for convection-diffusion problems. Part II: fully discretized scheme and numerical results*, *SIAM. J. Numer. Anal.*, 50 (2012), pp. 2824–2844.
- [6] ———, *Pure Lagrangian and semi-Lagrangian finite element methods for the numerical solution of convection-diffusion problems*, *Int. J. Numer. Anal. Mod.*, 11 (2014), pp. 271–287.
- [7] A. BERMÚDEZ AND J. DURANY, *La méthode des caractéristiques pour des problèmes de convection-diffusion stationnaires*, *M2AN. Math. Mod. and Num. Anal.*, 21 (1987), pp. 7–26.
- [8] A. BERMÚDEZ, M. R. NOGUEIRAS, AND C. VÁZQUEZ, *Numerical analysis of convection-diffusion-reaction problems with higher order characteristics/finite elements. Part I: Time discretization*, *SIAM. J. Numer. Anal.*, 44 (2006), pp. 1829–1853.
- [9] ———, *Numerical analysis of convection-diffusion-reaction problems with higher order characteristics/finite elements. Part II: Fully discretized scheme and quadrature formulas*, *SIAM. J. Numer. Anal.*, 44 (2006), pp. 1854–1876.
- [10] K. CHRYSAFINOS AND N. J. WALKINGTON, *Error estimates for discontinuous Galerkin approximations of implicit parabolic equations*, *SIAM J. Numer. Anal.*, 43 (2006), pp. 2478–2499.
- [11] ———, *Error estimates for the discontinuous Galerkin methods for parabolic equations*, *SIAM J. Numer. Anal.*, 44 (2006), pp. 349–366.
- [12] ———, *Lagrangian and moving mesh methods for the convection diffusion equation*, *M2AN Math. Model. Numer. Anal.*, 42 (2008), pp. 25–55.
- [13] J. DOUGLAS, JR., AND T. F. RUSSELL, *Numerical methods for convection-dominated diffusion problems based on combining the method of characteristics with finite element or finite difference procedures*, *SIAM J. Numer. Anal.*, 19 (1982), pp. 871–885.
- [14] R. E. EWING AND H. WANG, *A summary of numerical methods for time-dependent advection-dominated partial differential equations*, *J. Comput. Appl. Math.*, 128 (2001), pp. 423–445.
- [15] R. GLOWINSKI, T. W. PAN, T. I. HESLA, D. D. JOSEPH, AND J. PÉRIAUXX, *A fictitious domain approach to the direct numerical simulation of incompressible viscous flow past moving rigid bodies: application to particulate flow*, *J. Comput. Phys.*, 169 (2001), pp. 363–423.
- [16] M. E. GURTIN, *An Introduction to Continuum Mechanics*, vol. 158, Academic Press, San Diego, 1981.
- [17] A. HUERTA AND W. K. LIU, *Viscous flow with large free surface motion*, *Comput. Methods Appl. Mech. Engrg.*, 69 (1988), pp. 277–324.
- [18] O. PIRONNEAU, *On the transport-diffusion algorithm and its applications to the Navier-Stokes equations*, *Numer. Math.*, 38 (1982), pp. 309–332.
- [19] H. RUI AND M. TABATA, *A second order characteristic finite element scheme for convection-diffusion problems*, *Numer. Math.*, 92 (2002), pp. 161–177.
- [20] M. SOULI AND J. P. ZOLESIO, *Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian and free surface methods in fluid mechanics*, *Comput. Methods Appl. Mech. Engrg.*, 191 (2001), pp. 451–466.
- [21] E. SÜLI, *Stability and convergence of the Lagrange-Galerkin method with non-exact integration*. *Academic Press, London*, *The mathematics of finite elements and applications*, VI, (1988), pp. 435–442.